

TECHNOLOGY OF TEACHING FOREIGN LANGUAGES TO THE STUDENTS OF EXACT AND NATURAL SCIENCES IN HIGHER EDUCATIONAL INSTITUTIONS OF TURKMENISTAN

Nasiba Ikramovna Kurambayeva*

Oguz Han Engineering and Technology University of Turkmenistan, Ashgabat, Turkmenistan.

*Corresponding author

Under the leadership of our leader the Epoch of happiness Turkmen people moves forward with great strength. Highly esteemed Hero Arkadag several times noted that socio-economical development should be the care of the society. In the Revival Era of a Powerful State, every day of the year, held under the motto “The Epoch of the People with Arkadag”, which will be inscribed in golden letters in the history of the Motherland, marked by important events and labor achievements to maintain the development of our country in various spheres of life: “The development of socio-humanitarian aspects of science for 2018-2023 state program”, “To transfer the science into the digital system program for the 2020-2025 years”, “The concept of the promotion digital system in Turkmenistan”, “The concept of improving the methods of teaching foreign languages in Turkmenistan.” For that reasons our President follows the above policy to introduce the world experience into the process of education. There are several higher educational establishments where students gain knowledge in the following disciplines: Math, Informatics, natural and exact sciences, humanitarian sciences and foreign languages.

At Oguz han Engineering and Technology University of Turkmenistan there are all opportunities to implement all concept for fruitful studies. In the book “Source of wisdom” written by Hero Arkad ag there are many lines devoted to the learning languages. We teach students not only English but also Japanese too. As teachers, we pay great attention to the extra curriculum activities, such as: round tables, contests, “brain rings”, discussions and debates. The Russian professor G. A. Kitaygorodskaya mentioned that each student is certainly an individual and we can not teach them all according to the same method or technology, but a master pedagogue-teacher will be able to determine the end. There is a language barrier in students learning foreign languages, and in order to overcome it, the role of the teacher to make the young generation perfect individuals is also great. Learning a foreign language does not mean mastering the system of that language, but rather learning the history, origin, and culture of the language you are learning. Thus, a foreign language teacher uses various pedagogical technologies to master the material. Today, there are several types of pedagogical technologies, which are complex systems consisting of images that combine teaching technology, conceptually related educational goals, various types of resources, methods of organizing learning and educational processes. Another thing that should be noted is pedagogical technologies in the direction of personal structures, which are divided into the following types: informational (the formation of basic knowledge and skills), practical (the technology that ensures the formation of mental actions) and self-development).

At the university, students, studying at the language learning department cover scientific materials and texts, and also, they do some exercises related to their profession in English.

During the course, students also learn special terms and words. After all, students studying technical and scientific courses are not only familiar with the vocabulary of standard English, but also with technical and academic terms related to their major. In English lessons, taking into account the students' psychological abilities, they are given guiding introductory questions related to the topic to avoid problems before starting a new topic. Also, difficulties are eliminated through new innovative strategies called know, want to know, learned, and students learn new words and information during the lesson through Total physical response. In order to develop the language skills of students who study in a natural and exact science to revise the topics which were covered, all kinds of discussion, brainstorming, action games to check their fluency, and spelling tests using cards are used during the lesson. Also, producing videos related to their majors in English and Japanese at the university lab is also great way to develop a foreign language among the students.

Content and language integrated learning, Bloom's taxonomy, Critical thinking, Case technology, game and problem-solving technology are used as technologies to teach students not only by foreign language teachers at the university, but also by natural and exact sciences: physics, chemistry, biology, informatics, philology, mathematics and ecology. The technologies, methods and strategies operating in the 20th century are different from the present century, that is students are taught through group, two-to-one, and one-to-one methods to improve life skills in students. It will improve their way of thinking, language skills and worldview.

The topic of the condition provides a chance for any student to express his own judgment and also to assist in the development of a general resolution, which will be thrown out for consideration. With such a role, modern technologies of teaching foreign languages allow us to come to the conclusion that at present there are two main ways to intensify the learning process: one - by maximizing the use of technical means, the other – by activating the reserves of the personality of each student. It was found out that at Oguz han Engineering and Technology University of Turkmenistan these methods show high results for students and it will also be improved in the nearest future.

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